

PROFICIENCY OF “GURU PENGGERAK” IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN MATHEMATICS LEARNING: A REVIEW OF THE TPACK FRAMEWORK

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Abstract

This study was conducted to analyze the ability of Grade 1 transformational teachers or “*guru penggerak*” in TPACK-integrated mathematics learning at SDN Krapyakrejo II, Pasuruan City. TPACK is one of the references that combines technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge into one and is considered important in the 21st century. This research used a qualitative approach with a case study, which involved the first-grade transformational teacher of SDN Krapyakrejo II, Pasuruan City. Data were collected through observations, interviews and documents related to lesson planning and implementation. The findings show that teachers have mastered the mathematics content and pedagogical skills appropriate for grade I students well. But the integration of technology in learning still needs to be improved, especially in the effective integration of technology to support mathematics learning. Professional development for grade one teachers needs to be directed towards improving technological competencies integrated with content and pedagogy to enable more innovative and more effective learning to take place in the classroom.

Keywords: Teacher, Elementary School, Mathematics Learning, TPACK.

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the basic elements in building a nation. Quality education will produce superior human resources who are able to compete in global life (Marsitin et al., 2022). This means that educators are not only expected to master their subject matter but also learn how to optimally use technology in the learning process (Li, 2023). It is in this context that something called Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge called TPACK emerges. TPACK is a framework that teaches teachers how technology, pedagogy, and content come together in learning (Kong & Lai, 2022).

The TPACK framework is a development of the pedagogical content knowledge model, which was first described by Shulman in 1986 (McComas, 2014). According to Shulman, a good teacher should combine knowledge in subject content with appropriate teaching methods. Later, Koehler et al. (2013) added a technology component to this concept and developed the TPACK framework in 2006. They argued that TPACK consists of three main components: Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), and Content Knowledge (CK). Their combination is expected to bring more interactive, engaging, and relevant learning to meet the needs of 21st century students (Sa'dijah et al., 2023).

Mathematics learning plays an important role in the basic education level, especially in Grade 1 of Primary School. Mathematics has been considered as the foundation in the development of students' cognitive abilities, especially in terms of logical thinking, problem solving, and critical thinking (Sadjah et al., 2021). Mathematics teachers in grade 1 face the biggest challenge in introducing basic mathematical concepts that are simple, understandable, and internalized by students who have just started formal learning. In this case, the right approach to learning is to ensure that there is a strong development of understanding from an early age.

In this context, the ability of teachers becomes very important. Teachers are those who have more ability to carry out the learning process, stimulate positive change, and act as agents of innovation in the school context (Lyublinskaya & Tournaki, 2013). They can act not only as learning facilitators but also as inspirers who are able to push students towards creative and innovative types of learning (Agustini et al., 2019). Therefore, the transformational teacher or *guru penggerak* is expected to be able to effectively apply the TPACK framework in mathematics learning in Grade 1 elementary school.

The challenges associated with implementing TPACK in mathematics learning cannot be ignored. Most teachers still experience obstacles in integrating technology into learning (Voithofer & Nelson, 2021), especially in areas where technology infrastructure is inadequate. Some teachers also feel that they are not confident enough or trained enough in using technology as part of the teaching process (Jin & Harp, 2020). Actually, the integration of technology into the mathematics learning process will provide students with better opportunities to visualize abstract ideas through visualization tools, simulations, and educational games (Sintawati & Abdurrahman, 2020). In addition, the role of technology is increasingly important in education today, with government programs increasingly encouraging digitalization through policies such as "Merdeka Belajar" (Iskandar et al., 2021). Transformational teachers should not only understand the theoretical framework related to technology in learning but they should also be able to apply it practically in the daily classroom context (Elvianasti et al., 2023). In this way, students will be able to learn mathematics in a more interesting and relevant way thus improving their learning motivation and learning outcomes.

This study analyzes the ability of transformational teachers in learning mathematics in grade 1 elementary school based on the TPACK framework. This research is important because it can provide a clear picture of the extent to which teacher mobilizers are able to integrate technology, pedagogy and content in mathematics learning. The results are expected to provide insights to education policy makers in designing training and professional development programs for teachers, especially those related to teachers' mastery of TPACK.

This research can also be used as a reference for schools and teachers to develop more effective and technology-based learning strategies. Technology in mathematics learning can serve as a means to improve students' acquisition of basic concepts through visualization and interactivity (Rufiana et al., 2020). In addition, through the use of technology, teachers can provide a more collaborative and participatory environment for students; that is, students will have the opportunity to learn actively through different types of media.

Third, this research is related to the current global challenges in education, where digitization of education is included in the top priorities (Miguel-revilla et al., 2020). Since technological skills are included in the competencies that students should have in the 21st century, teachers should be the driving force in encouraging students' mastery of technology. Therefore, this raises the need to establish the extent to which teacher leaders are able to integrate technology into learning, especially in early grade mathematics learning.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design and Research Subjects

This study uses a qualitative case study approach that specifically investigates the ability of Grade 1 teachers of SDN Krapyakrejo II in TPACK-integrated mathematics learning. The use of qualitative research is to describe events that occur in research subjects and data collected without the purpose of generalization. This research can provide a thorough in-depth understanding of the lead teachers' ability to integrate technology, pedagogy and mathematics content. Such qualitative studies will help researchers to gain a more in-depth view of teachers' behaviors, perceptions, and actions in real classroom situations.

Data Collection

To fulfill the research objectives, the data collection techniques used were:

1. Observation

Classroom observations were conducted to observe the mathematics learning process integrated with TPACK in Grade 1 at SDN Krapyakrejo II. Classroom observations were conducted systematically using an observation guide focused on the elements of the TPACK framework. The objectives of this classroom observation were (1) how teachers use technology, both hardware and software; (2) how teachers deliver math materials, the pedagogical methods used, and how students respond to learning. These observations are important to capture classroom dynamics, interactions between teachers and students, and the extent to which technology is applied in the teaching and learning process. In this observation, specific aspects such as: (a) The use of technology including the use of math software, visual tools, or other digital devices; (b) The pedagogy applied such as discussion methods, question and answer; and (c) How mathematical content is applied in teaching, for example, the introduction of basic number concepts and addition and subtraction operations under the guidance of the teacher is carefully observed.

2. Interview with “Guru Penggerak”

In-depth interviews were conducted with Grade I teachers who were the subject of the study to gather information about teachers' perspectives, experiences and challenges in integrating technology with pedagogy and mathematics content in teaching. The questions asked in the interviews were as follows: (1) teachers' conceptions of TPACK; (2) experiences related to the use of technology in learning; (3) strategies in teaching mathematics content to grade I students; (4) teachers' perceptions of how technology is used to improve students' understanding; (5)

barriers to effective integration of technology into classroom practices e.g. lack of access to technology and lack of training, and steps taken by teachers to overcome these challenges.

Data Analysis

Data analysis in this study used thematic analysis with a qualitative descriptive approach. Data obtained from classroom observations and in-depth interviews with *guru penggerak* as well as analysis of related documents were summarized, grouped, and interpreted to find patterns and main themes relevant to the research focus. Data analysis began with data reduction, namely filtering information related to mastery of content, pedagogy, and technology in mathematics learning based on the TPACK framework. Next, the data was categorized into themes, such as learning strategies, constraints on the use of technology, and the level of student engagement. Then, further themes were analyzed to find the association of teachers' TPACK mastery with students' learning outcomes. Data interpretation was supported by relevant theories and linked to previous findings. The results of this analysis are then made into a descriptive narrative to provide a comprehensive picture of the competence of *guru penggerak* the integration of technology, pedagogy and content in mathematics learning in Grade 1.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of this research is to study the ability of driving teachers to integrate technology, pedagogy, and content in mathematics learning in grade 1 using the TPACK framework. The results of the questionnaire were analyzed according to the TPACK framework consisting of indicators of content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and technological knowledge.

Content Knowledge Mastery (CK)

The use of concrete learning media is very effective for early childhood students because they are still at the concrete operational stage of development, where physical manipulation of objects can help them understand abstract concepts. This approach also makes learning more interactive and fun, thus increasing students' engagement in the learning process. Teachers demonstrate an excellent understanding of the mathematical materials related to grade 1 teaching, which include simple topics such as number recognition, addition and subtraction. These materials are delivered in a simple manner and adapted to students' cognitive development levels.

In addition, *guru penggerak* is also able to design creative learning activities to help students understand basic mathematics concepts (Kim, 2018). Teachers use physical aids, such as objects that are easily recognizable to students, to reinforce students' understanding of basic operations. For example, in teaching addition, teachers use small objects such as buttons, sticks, bottle caps, matchsticks or stones to visualize the addition process to students. Thus, students can manipulate the objects directly so that they can understand abstract conceptions more concretely. This way of teaching is simple and relevant as it allows students to interact directly with the learning materials and ultimately build a solid foundation of mathematical understanding that is appropriate to their developmental stage (Altun & Yildirim, 2023).

Figure 1: Visual aids used by the teachers in teaching number addition

While content mastery is excellent, sometimes turning abstract math concepts into language that Grade 1 students can easily understand can be challenging. This is especially true when teaching complex or abstract concepts, such as those in math operations that may involve more than one step. Some of these solve this problem through the use of physical or visual manipulative media in accordance with the real world of students. In accordance with the interview with the teacher, namely:

"Anticipating and identifying difficult math concepts for students is an important part of effective lesson planning. Here are some steps I usually take to help facilitate students' understanding of these concepts: Learning from previous teaching experiences, Discussions with peers, Using open-ended question and answer techniques, Simplifying concepts through analogies and visualizations, Providing Variations in Learning Methods, Utilizing technology, etc."

The interview above illustrates the teacher's efforts in designing effective lessons to overcome difficult math concepts for students. Steps such as learning from previous teaching experiences, discussing with peers, and using open-ended questioning techniques demonstrate a reflective and collaborative approach in understanding students' difficulties. Analogy and visualization are used as clever strategies to make abstract concepts simpler (Amador, 2022). The variety of learning methods and the utilization of technology show a commitment to presenting learning that is interesting and in line with the times (Lyublinskaya & Du, 2022). Overall, it reflects educators' readiness to help students understand the material better, make learning more interactive, and generate student confidence in learning mathematics (Arifin et al., 2024).

Mastery of Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)

From the observation, it was found that the *guru penggerak* is accustomed to using various approaches when teaching basic math concepts, such as the use of group discussion methods, problem-based learning, and contextual learning. The technology-integrated approach in grade 1 math learning used by teachers is interactive games or activities that can help them understand basic math concepts (Arifin et al., 2024), especially for Grade 1 students who are still in the early stages of cognitive development. Teachers teach the concepts of addition and subtraction,

for example, using physical games involving bottle caps, sticks, longan fruit seeds and buttons with the aim of students better understanding these concepts.

"Using various student-centered learning strategies and models is an effective approach to significantly improve student engagement and understanding. Teachers can create a more dynamic learning environment and support the development of students' critical thinking skills and creativity by engaging students in active learning processes, providing freedom for exploration, and encouraging collaboration".

The implementation of student-oriented learning strategies and models by teachers not only makes the learning process more dynamic, but also provides support to students to develop their critical thinking skills and creativity. By providing opportunities for exploration and encouraging collaboration, teachers help students become active participants in their own learning process, so that learning becomes a meaningful and relevant experience (Nurin et al., 2024). This is in accordance with the results of the teacher interview, namely:

"Designing learning that encourages students to actively engage and develop critical thinking skills is a must, designing learning that encourages students to actively engage and develop critical thinking skills requires diverse and innovative approaches. Through methods such as project-based learning, collaboration, open-ended questions, and reflection, students will be trained to think more critically and creatively in dealing with everyday problems"

Effective learning is about making students active and critical learners. For example, project-based learning, collaboration, open-ended questions, and reflection, all these approaches are very important in building critical thinking skills among students, particularly in solving real-life challenges. In this case, learning activities will involve students actively, so that they are not just receiving information in a passive way, but are trained to disseminate, spread, and find creative solutions (Rufiana et al., 2024). This strategy not only enriches the learning experience, but also helps students develop important 21st century skills, such as problem solving, cooperation, and communication. Therefore, the role of teachers is crucial in planning learning activities that are not only academically relevant, but also contextual and meaningful to students' lives.

Figure 2: Math learning using props and technology

Classroom learning activities that involve students directly through the use of concrete aids (Ekawati et al., 2024). In this picture, some students are interacting with various objects such as bottle caps, wooden sticks and seeds to understand basic math concepts. This activity is an experiential learning approach that emphasizes the manipulation of physical objects to help students build abstract concepts, such as addition or subtraction, more strongly. It is particularly suitable for early grade students as it engages them actively, improves fine motor skills, and makes learning more fun and meaningful.

"Facilitating discussions and collaborative activities in grade 1 through approaches such as problem-based learning, inquiry-based learning, collaborative learning, and project-based learning are effective strategies to help students exchange ideas and strengthen their understanding, while also helping them develop social and critical thinking skills."

Learning in grade 1 is geared towards supporting students' cognitive and social development by facilitating discussions and collaborative activities, such as problem-based, inquiry, collaborative and project learning. In this way, students can learn in an active-participatory way to exchange ideas, develop cooperation, and find solutions to simple problems that often occur in everyday life. This strategy also helps students develop higher-order intelligence skills, such as analyzing, evaluating, and making decisions (Lefrida et al., 2023). Even further, the interaction between members in small groups strengthens their social skills, namely communication, respect for others' opinions, and can develop cooperation.

Mastery of Technology Knowledge (TK)

Guru penggerak is aware of available technology, such as the use of projectors, learning videos, and other simple applications such as *Microsoft PowerPoint*, *youtube canva*, *kahoot*, *wordwall*, and *quizizz*.

*"Integrating technology with student-centered learning strategies in Grade 1 can increase student engagement and encourage critical thinking skills by using interactive tools such as digital whiteboards where students are invited to play games like **Kahoot!**, **wordwall**, or **Quizizz** where they have to solve challenges and answer questions. These games require critical thinking and analysis to achieve the goal, while still having fun"*.

Figure 3: Technology-based learning

The learning atmosphere in grade 1 elementary school, where students look focused on following the ongoing activities. The teacher uses the media projector as a learning tool to display materials or videos relevant to the topic being taught. The students sit at their desks neatly, showing their engagement in the learning process. The use of technology such as projectors in this classroom provides added value by providing an interesting visual experience, so that students more easily understand the material being taught (Amaliah et al., 2023) . This is in accordance with the teacher interview, namely:

"Customizing the use of technology based on student needs and characteristics is key to creating effective and relevant learning experiences. To understand students' learning preferences we must be able to recognize students' backgrounds, interests and learning styles."

Tailoring the use of technology to students' needs and characteristics is an important step in creating effective and relevant learning experiences (Voithofer et al., 2019). The technology used must be able to answer the needs of individual students and support the learning process according to their stage of development. For this reason, teachers must be familiar with students' backgrounds, both social, cultural, and environmental conditions, so that they can choose the approach that best suits the students (Lemmo, 2021). In addition, understanding students' interests helps teachers create interesting and motivating learning, while recognizing learning styles be it visual, auditory, or kinesthetic allows technology to be used in a more optimal way. By integrating such understanding, technology-based learning becomes not only a support tool, but also a personalized and meaningful experience for students.

*"Selecting and effectively managing technology to improve the conceptual understanding of grade 1 students requires a careful and strategic approach. Choose tools and apps that match the needs of the students and the learning objectives. Look for educational apps that support math learning, such as **Kahoot!**, **wordwall**, or **Quizizz**, or other visual teaching apps. Ensure that the technology is easy to use and engaging for grade 1 students."*

Thus, choosing and effectively managing technology to improve conceptual understanding of grade 1 students must be done carefully and strategically. Learners or teachers must be selective in choosing tools or applications according to student needs and learning objectives, especially in basic math concepts such as number recognition, addition, and subtraction. *Kahoot!*, *Wordwall* or *Quizizz* apps can be an interesting choice as they offer interactive features that motivate students to learn while playing. In addition, visual teaching technologies such as animated videos or simple simulations can also be used to clarify abstract concepts (Estapa & Davis, 2023). The most important thing is that the chosen tool or application is child-friendly, easy to use, and appropriate for the developmental stage of grade 1 students. So that the technology is not only interesting but also truly effective in supporting learning.

Teachers should ensure that the apps or tools used do not distract students from the main cognitive objectives. Technology should be used to enrich the learning experience and should not replace direct interaction with the teacher or shared learning activities in the classroom (Antony et al., 2019). Therefore, it is important for teachers to develop lesson plans that integrate technology with other learning methods, such as activity-based learning, group

discussions or collaborative projects, to ensure students remain actively engaged and have the opportunity to develop social skills and critical thinking. This approach to learning that combines technology with traditional methods also allows students to experience more holistic and balanced learning. Technology can be used to introduce new concepts through engaging visualizations or interactive simulations, while collaborative classroom activities, such as group discussions or projects, provide opportunities for students to share ideas, work together, and learn from each other (Estapa & Davis, 2023). In this way, students not only acquire more in-depth knowledge, but also develop important social and emotional skills, such as communication, empathy, and teamwork. Teachers have a very important role in facilitating these interactions, by ensuring that technology is used to support, not replace, student-oriented learning experiences. In this way, the use of technology not only enhances students' conceptual understanding, but also supports their development of 21st century skills, such as creativity, collaboration and problem solving (King, 2018).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that transformational teacher or in Indonesia we called it as *guru penggerak* has a good understanding of grade 1 math content and is able to deliver it in a way that is adapted to students' cognitive development. Teachers master learning techniques that involve physical activities and simple tools to reinforce understanding of basic math concepts, such as addition and subtraction. However, the use of technology in learning still faces challenges, especially in terms of proper integration to keep students focused and actively engaged. Technology tends to be used as a visual aid rather than an integral component in an interactive learning process. To achieve effective TPACK-based learning, teachers need more in-depth training and access to relevant technology to optimize mathematics learning with technology in a synergistic manner. This is expected to improve the quality of learning and help students develop a better understanding of mathematics from an early age.

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